

RELATIONSHIPS OF FORM AND MEANING IN JADID POETRY

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Abstract. *In this article, the lexical units in the language of the poetry of the Jadids, who lived in the beginning of the 20th century and left their indelible mark, are analyzed according to the relationship of form and meaning. In particular, modern poetry was analyzed separately from the point of view of lexical units of the language.*

Key words: *20th century, repression, poetry, creativity, modernity, enlightenment, language, unity, era, thinker, homeland, unity, meaning, work, sema, lexeme, e' attention.*

ВЗАИМООТНОШЕНИЯ ФОРМЫ И СМЫСЛА В ПОЭЗИИ ДЖАДИДОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье лексические единицы в языке поэзии джадидов, живших в начале XX века и оставивших свой неизгладимый след, анализируются с точки зрения взаимоотношений формы и смысла. В частности, отдельно анализировалась современная поэзия с точки зрения лексических единиц языка.*

Ключевые слова: *XX век, репрессии, поэзия, творчество, современность, просвещение, язык, единство, эпоха, мыслитель, родина, единство, смысл, произведение, сема, лексема, внимание.*

In the history of our country, the situation at the beginning of the 20th century, social and political changes led to the change of the national speech art both in terms of content and form.

Jadid poetry occupies a special place among the artists who appeared at the beginning of the last century. Almost the same genre in poetry, which had been the dominant form of the language for many years, was renewed during this period. Aruz remained the leading weight until the 20s of the 20th century. "It is known that Aruz has been the leading weight of Uzbek poetry for ten centuries, starting with "Kutadgu bilig". Even during this long-term "triumphant march" of Aruz, without denying that there were changes, growths and processes that prepared its negation, the rules of Aruz took the shape of a strict pattern and maintained this status until the beginning of the 20th century. Jadid Aruzi also first appeared in these traditional forms.¹

¹ Афокова Н. Жадид шеърляти поэтикаси. – Тошкент: Фан, 2005. – Б. 13.

The motif of love, which formed the main part of classical Uzbek lyrics, was mainly associated with two objects - the earthly lover and God. Jadid poets drastically changed this direction in lyrics. It can be said that putting the people and the nation in the center as a lover was a revolution in national poetry. In this way, the images of the poet, lover, flower, and nightingale in the lyrics of modern poets were connected with the fate of the Motherland and the nation.

It is known that the word "jadid" means "new", "innovation". There has never been a place and time in the history of mankind, when the innovation that entered the life of the society was not met with great resistance. The harmony of society and human life will sooner or later lead to decline.

That is why the leading intellectuals of the people "develop" new ideas to fight against or prevent the decline that started yesterday in society and human life. But some people who live in the "hot bosom" of this recession, who have developed such skills, welcome these life-giving ideas with a spear. Such a situation occurred in Central Asia at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. The modern enlightenment movement that started in Turkestan, Bukhara and Khiva, as well as in some foreign countries of the East, faced great obstacles.

The Jadids, who lived in the harsh colonial era, withstood all the difficulties, and finally gave up, left behind a rich spiritual heritage. Science and enlightenment, religion, truth, humanity, values and traditions were able to sacrifice not only their creativity, but also their lives. The weight of our ancestors, especially their poetry, has an important place. One of the tasks of the Jadids, who are representatives of the national renaissance period, was aimed at awakening the sleepy people and enlightening them by praising the concepts of the homeland, people, nation, and development through poetry. .

As a society enters a period of intense development, a specific development may occur in the language. A new layer of words (neologisms) appears in the speech, they become popularized, reflect the spirit of the people more and more widely.

In linguistics, each language unit has its own importance, and the field of semasiology is one of these fields. Semasiology is also called semantics. Since semantics studies the meanings of words and phrases in the text and outside the text, the issues of semantic analysis are of great importance in linguistics. Each language has its own characteristics, and their language characteristics are related to culture. At this point, we can say that the general outlook of the nation can show its uniqueness in linguistics.

In Jadid's poetry, the semantic features of the language are expressed in a special way.

Come, angel, come, come, fairy, come, come, kiss, caress,

Come kiss the sunrise... come kiss one morning,

Come, hug, come, let me see your hand, your finger,
 Come, look into your eyes, come, (?) see, then die...
 Don't come, don't come, fairy, you, your body is your light,
 Your bodies are light, your faces are light, your equals are yours...
 Know it from the oil poured from the burning moons,
 All the stars on the blue face are yours...²

Learning words can be divided into:

1. Synonymy - the same symbol can be represented by several symbols appears when there is, for example: malak, pari; light, rain, etc.
2. Antonym - is characterized because a sign has the opposite meaning to another, for example: cold - hot.
3. Polysemy - occurs when the referent corresponds to more than one meaning, if there is a word face, it corresponds to both blue and human face.
4. Homonymy is the similarity of meanings, homonyms are different when writing words, for example: blue - sky, places (have verb) and tube (cylindrical object).

Semantics or semasiology studies and analyzes the meaning of words and phrases in linguistics. That is, it is a branch of science that studies the meaning of words in the process of speech or writing. This field was first introduced into linguistics as a separate field by Michel Bréal in 1833.

REFERENCES

1. Афоқова Н. Жадид шеърятти поэтикаси. – Тошкент: Фан, 2005. – Б. 13.
2. Чўлпон. Гўзал Туркистон. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 1997. – Б. 31. Чўлпон. Асарлар. Уч жилдлик. 1-жилд. – Тошкент, 1993.– Б. 7.
3. A.Sodiqov, A.Abduazizov, M.Irisqulov. Tilshunoslikka kirish. T.: “Fan”, 1981. 95-b.
4. U.Tursunov. Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili. T.: “O‘zbekiston”, 1992. 66-b.
5. O‘sha manba. 98-b.
6. M.Yo‘ldoshev. Cho‘lpon so‘zining sirlari. T.: “Ma’naviyat”, 2002. 23-b.
7. M.Mirtojiyev. O‘zbek tilida polisemiya. - Toshkent: Fan nashriyoti, 1984. -136-b.
8. B.Suyunov. Omonimiyaning polisemiya dan farqi. Til va adabiyot ta’limi. 2002. №3, 43-44-b.

² Чўлпон. Гўзал Туркистон. – Тошкент: Маънавият, 1997. – Б. 31. Чўлпон. Асарлар. Уч жилдлик. 1-жилд. – Тошкент, 1993.– Б. 7.

9. Cho'lpon. Yana oldim sozimni. T.: "Cho'lpon", 1991. 13-b.
10. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. T. 2008. T.: 332,465-b.
11. V.Rahmonov. O'zbek klassik adabiyoti asarlari uchun qisqacha lug'at. T.: "O'qituvchi", 1983. 182-b.
12. Komilovna, I. N. Ziyo Distributed From Tezguzar. JournalNX, 30-33.
13. Komilovna, I. N. (2022). Ibrahim Muminov's Scientific and Philosophical Heritage and Subjective Approaches to His Scientific Activity Under the Rule of the Former Ideology. International Journal on Integrated Education, 5(6), 556-559.
14. Ibodova, N. K. (2023). ALI QUSHCHI FAOLIYATINI TADQIQ ETISHDA IBROHIM MO 'MINOVNING ROLI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 3(2), 824-829.
15. Komilovna, I. N. (2024). Philosophical Lines to Academician Ibrahim Muminov's Activity. Journal of Sustainability in Integrated Policy and Practice, 2(1), 15-18.
16. Ibodova, N. K. (2024). THE ROLE OF IBRAHIM MOMINOV IN STUDYING THE PERSONALITY OF AMIR TEMUR. INTERNATIONAL SCIENCES, EDUCATION AND NEW LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES, 1(4), 154-157.
17. Ibodova, N. (2024). ACADEMIC IBRAHIM MOMINOV: MY FIRST TEACHER IS MY MOTHER. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 3(4 SPECIAL), 436-438.
18. İbodova, N., & Raupova, R. (2023). ÖZBEK EDEBİYATI DİLİNİN MODERNİTE DÖNEMİNDE GELİŞİMİNDE ÇOLPON'UN ROLÜ. Philological issues are in the eyes of young researchers, 1(1). 2023
19. Ibodova Nasiba Komilovna. (2024). ANALYSIS OF IBRAHIM MOMINOV'S CREATION OF ABU RAYHAN BERUNI. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(4), 359–365. извлечено от <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/mpttp/article/view/5153>
20. Ibodov G. K. (2023). KLASSIK VA MAXSUS - YORDAMCHI MASHQLARNING YUKLAMA ME'YORI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(15), 13–16. Retrieved from <http://erus.uz/index.php/er/article/view/4660>
21. Ibodov Ghalibjon Komilovich. Classic And Special -The Loading Standards of Assistant Exercises. Journal of Sustainability Integrated Policy and Practice. 2024. 19-21-p. <https://journals.proindex.uz/index.php/SIPP/article/view/485/419>